

Adaptive Reasoning Profile Field-Dependent And Field-Independent Cognitive Style Of Students In Planing Solutions To Solve The Math-Problem

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 01 , 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 02, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Adaptive Reasoning, Planning Solutions, Field Dependent, Field Independent.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5750029</p>	<p><i>This study aims to describe the adaptive reasoning profile of students who have a field-dependent cognitive style (FDCS) and a field-independent cognitive style (FICS) in making plans for solving mathematical problems. This research is a searching-descriptive study with a qualitative approach. The instruments used were the Group Embedded Figures Test (GEFT), Adaptive Reasoning Test (TPA), and interview guidelines. The results showed profile, adaptive reasoning FDCS, and FICS in planning solutions to solve math-problem are making models by relating the situation to the concept and explaining the reasons, relating the situation to the situation and explaining the reason, linking the concept with the concept and explain the reason. FICS subjects are analytical in relating concepts to problem situations, while FDCS subjects have difficulty finding relationships between a situation and situation.</i></p>

Introduction

Logical thinking is a reasoning and correct thinking activity following previously known knowledge (Siswono, 2008; Suriasumantri, 2017). Furthermore, logical thinking interpreted as reasoning and reasoning is one of the standard process standards (NCTM, 2000). Reasoning that connects existing facts or information to form a conclusion (Douglass et al., 2012; NCTM, 2000; Suharnan, 2005; Suriasumantri, 2017). If a student is asked to solve a math problem, then he must make an appropriate plan by considering (1) conceptual understanding, (2) procedural fluency, (3) strategic competence, (4) adaptive reasoning, (5) productive disposition (NRC, 2001).

Adaptive reasoning is the capacity to think logically about the relationship between concepts and situations. So that the reasoning will be valid based on the alternative arguments given, and the ability to provide conclusions (NRC, 2001). Adaptive reasoning is a logical thinking process by connecting concepts and situations not only to make conclusions but also to provide reasons and assess or check the truth of an argument (C. F. Haryanti & Masriyah, 2017; M. D. Haryanti & Wibowo, 2016; Ostler, 2011). Thinking process in problem-solving, the teacher should get the attention, especially to develop students to get used to thinking logically (Cooney et al., 1975). Adaptive reasoning is closely related to problem-solving because it plays a role as a determinant of the legitimacy of problem-solving strategies (Maharani & Rosyidi, 2018; NRC, 2001; Siegfried, 2012). When students are given a problem, each individual has a different way of dealing with problems according to their cognitive style (Akramunnisa & Sulestry, 2016; Witkin et al., 1977; Aning W. Yanti et al., 2020), cognitive style is an individual character and a consistent approach in organizing and processing information.

Field-dependent cognitive style (FDCS) and a field-independent cognitive style (FICS) influence reasoning, namely adaptive reasoning. According to Witkin et al. (1977), the cognitive style consists of FDCS and FISC, where students whom FICS tend to perceive separate parts of a pattern according to its components, while students who have the FD cognitive style tend to perceive a pattern as a whole and are difficult to interpret. Focus on one aspect of a situation or analyze a pattern into multiples. According to Bertini et al., (1986), suggests that FICS individuals are superior to FDCS individuals. It is certainly to study deeply how FICS and FDCS adaptive reasoning in planning solutions to solve mathematical problems. Based on the tendency of students, FICS and FDCS, are closely related to adaptive reasoning. Because adaptive reasoning is reasoning that provides opportunities for students to provide reasonable arguments based on mathematical properties when looking for relationships between concepts and situations. Students will have different strategies in understanding, choosing strategies, making conclusions, and providing arguments.

Adaptive reasoning can be seen in research (Kristanti & Kriswandani, 2018; Maharani & Rosyidi, 2018; Mahendra et al., 2015; Sadiyah & Siswono, 2018; Suhendra et al., 2016; Syukriani et al., 2016; Aning Wida Yanti et al., 2020). From several recommendations, if a teacher knows the reasoning potential of his students, then the teacher can plan and implement learning to increase the potential of students. Therefore, this study aims to describe the adaptive reasoning profile of mathematics education students who have FDCS and FICS in making plans for solving mathematical problems.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study was conducted to determine the perspective of adaptive reasoning of students with FDCS and FICS at the stage of planning problem-solving in solving mathematical problems, then describing the student profiles in an exploratory descriptive manner with a qualitative approach. In this study, the researcher used two instruments, namely: (1) the primary instrument was the researcher, (2) the secondary instrument, namely (a) the GEFT (Group Embedded Figures Test) test, (b) the Adaptive Reasoning Test (TPA), (c) Interview guidelines. This research be held on the mathematics education undergraduate in UIN Sunan Ampel Surabaya. Based on the results of the Group Embedded Figures Test (GEFT), subjects were selected and classified by FDCS and FICS. Next, determine the subjects of FDCS and FICS who have relatively the same gender and mathematical abilities. The technique of checking the validity of the data used in this study was a triangulation of time. Analytical data used the following stages: (1) Categorization/classification of data, (2) Data reduction, (3) Presentation of data and interpretation/interpretation of data, (4) Withdrawal conclusion.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In collecting data using the TPA Question as follows:

“Pak Ahmad has 57 stalls to sell fruit, each of which will be filled with the same number of oranges. Pak Ahmad bought 158 boxes. Each box contained the same amount of oranges and got a bonus 7 of oranges. All the oranges will send to all their stalls.
 a. How many oranges does each stall receive?
 b. how many oranges are in each box?
 (the capacity of the box is between 180 and 400 oranges)”

Adaptive Reasoning Profile of FDCS at Planning Solutions in Solving Mathematical Problems

FDCS subjects make models and plans by linking the situation to the concept, namely by linking the number of stalls, the number of boxes with the coefficient, the number of bonus oranges with the constant, and the number of oranges in each stall and boxes with the variables in the Diophantine equation. The subject of FDCS has not related the capacity of boxes of 180 to 400 oranges. This shows that the subject of FDCS has difficulty in capturing important information and finding the relationship between the situation and the concept following the opinion of Almolhodaie (2002). This is also following the characteristics of FDCS cognitive style students who tend to think globally and it is difficult for them to focus on analyzing a pattern into various types Witkin et al. (1977). Furthermore, the subject of FDCS gives a logical reason in determining the relationship between the situation and the concept, which can make it easier to do when the situation in the problem is the concepts of variables, coefficients, and constants will make it easier to do. These results indicate that the subject of FDCS thinks logically in formulating a plan to make a model by relating the situation to the concept as stated by Keraf (1999).

The subject of FDCS developed planning and making a model by relating the situation to the situation, by linking the number of oranges received by each stall with the number of stalls owned by Mr. Ahmad was 57 and linking the number of oranges in each box with 158 boxes. From this relationship, the subject of FDCS has not linked the number of bonus oranges, which are seven oranges and the capacity of the contents of the box is 180-400 oranges. Showed subject FDCS has difficulty knowing important information and finding the relationship between situations and situations following the opinion of Almolhodaie (2002). Following the characteristics of FDCS students who tend to think globally and difficult for them to focus on one aspect of a situation or analyze a pattern into various types as stated by Witkin et al. (1977). Furthermore, the subject FDCS provides a logical reason for the relationship of the situation to the situation, namely from situations that are known and related to each other. These results indicate that the subject of FDCS thinks logically in formulating a plan to make a model by linking the situation to the situation as stated by Keraf (1999).

Furthermore, the subject of FDCS developed a plan in making a model by linking concepts with concepts, namely linking the variables, coefficients, and constants with the Diophantine equations. However, the subject of FDCS has not linked the terms of the solution or constraint. Showed the subject of FDCS has difficulty finding a relationship between concepts and concepts following the opinion of Almolhodaie (2002). It also showed subject of FDCS subjects find it difficult to study unstructured materials (Wooldridge & Haimes-Bartolf, 2006). Following the characteristics of FDCS, tend to think globally and it is difficult for them to focus

on one aspect of the situation (Witkin et al., 1977). Furthermore, the subject of FDCS provides a logical reason for the relationship between the concept and the concept, namely when the equation is converted into a mathematical model using variables, coefficients, and constants, it will be the same as the general form of the Diophantine equation. These results indicate that the subject of FDCS thinks logically in formulating a plan to make a model by linking concepts with concepts as stated by Keraf (1999).

Then determine if the equation is a Diophantine equation or not. Solve the model using Euclid's Algorithm. But before finding the greatest common factor (GCF) from the number that represents the number of stalls and the number of squares, then prove or state the GCF as a linear combination of the two numbers, then solve the equation obtained by changing the equation according to the information in the problem. From the relationship determined by the subject of FDCS. There is a concept that isn't mentioned correctly, namely, the Euclidean Division Algorithm. The subject of FDCS mentions only Euclid's Algorithm and solving equations using the theorem where the subject of FDCS only mentions solving. This shows that the subject of FDCS has difficulty finding a relationship between concepts and concepts (Almolhodaie, 2002). This also shows that the subject of FDCS can not reconstruct the lessons that have been received (Wooldridge & Haimes-Bartolf, 2006). Furthermore, the subject of FDCS provides a logical reason for the relationship between the concept and the concept that has been determined, namely by using the relationship between the concept and the concept, the results will be obtained more quickly. These results indicate that the subject of FDCS thinks logically in developing plans to complete the model by linking concepts with concepts as stated by Keraf (1999).

These results indicate that the subject of FDCS in planning a solution can reason, as Keraf (1999) argues that the notion of reasoning is a thought process that seeks to connect known facts or evidence to a conclusion. These results also indicate that the subject of FDCS in planning a solution can reason adaptively, as stated by NRC (2001) that the notion of adaptive reasoning refers to the capacity to think logically about the relationship between concepts and situations.

Adaptive Reasoning Profile of FICS Subjects at the Stage of Planning Solutions in Solving Mathematical Problems

FICS subjects develop a plan to solve the problem by making a model by linking the situation with the concept, namely by doing the example of x = the number of oranges received in each stall and y = the number of oranges in each box, so that the number of oranges in each box and the number of oranges in each stall relates to the variables, relates the number of Pak Ahmad's stalls to the coefficient of the variable x , and the number of boxes to the coefficient of the variable y relates the number of citrus bonuses to the constants and the conditions given to the constraints that used to determine the Diophantine equation. FICS subjects have mentioned all situations with related concepts. Showed the subject of FICS can capture the core of the problem and is more analytical in relating the situation to the concept following the opinion of Almolhodaie (2002). The subject of FICS gives a logical reason in relating the situation to the concept, the situation described in the problem mathematical model according to the definition of the Diophantine equation in the form of the equation $ax + by = c$, where a, b, c are integers, and $a, b \neq 0$. Showed the FICS subject has excellent logical reasoning and analytical reasoning following the opinion of Holmes et al. (2013). These results indicate that FICS subjects think logically in formulating plans to make models by relating situations to concepts as stated by Keraf (1999)

Furthermore, the subject of FICS made planing solutions to solve a model by relating the situation to the situation. Determinate the relationship between the number of stalls, the number of boxes. The number of bonuses given to the oranges with the same number of oranges for each box. The number of oranges for each stall is distributed equally and the given requirements. The subject of FICS has mentioned all the situations in the problem and their relationship. This shows that FICS subjects can process information with their structure following the opinion of (Kuo et al., 2012). This also showed subject of FICS is more analytical in relating the situation to the situation following the opinion of Almolhodaie (2002). Showed the FICS subject can perform good analytical reasoning according to the opinion of Holmes et al. (2013). The subject of FICS gives a logical reason in relating the situation to this situation, namely adjusting the information on interrelated questions where the number of oranges in each box is the same and the number of oranges distributed in each stall fulfills the given requirements. These results indicate that the subject of FICS thinks logically in formulating a plan to make a model by relating the situation to the situation as stated by Keraf (1999).

Furthermore, the subject of FICS prepares a plan in making a model by linking concepts with concepts, namely linking the Diophantine equation with the coefficients, variables, constants, and requirements for problem solutions. The subject of FICS has mentioned all the linkages between concepts and concepts in making the model. Showed the subject of FICS can capture the core of the problem and is more analytical in connecting concepts with concepts according to the opinion of Almolhodaie (2002). Showed that the FICS subject can good perform analytical reasoning according to the opinion of Holmes et al. (2013). The subject of FICS gives a logical reason for linking the concept to the concept, namely based on the information contained in the problem according to the definition and requirements of the Diophantine equation. These results indicate

that the subject of FICS thinks logically in formulating a plan to make a model by linking concepts with concepts as stated by Keraf (1999). Then the subject of FICS draws up a plan to solve the Diophantine equation by linking it with the GCF concept using the Euclidean Division Algorithm, the concept of linear combination, the concept of a specific solution to an equation, the concept of a general solution of an equation, the concept of conditions for solving a problem. FICS subjects have mentioned all the linkages between concepts and concepts in completing the model. This shows that the subject of FICS has high independence in observing a problem following the opinion of Crowl et al. (1996). Showed the subject of FICS can capture the core of the problem and is more analytical in connecting concepts with concepts according to the opinion of Almolhodaie (2002). Following the characteristics of the FICS who tend to think analytically and can organize objects, and tend to perceive separate parts of a pattern according to its components as expressed by Witkin et al. (1977). The subject of FICS gives a logical reason for linking the concept to the concept in the model. Namely, the value of the variable is the answer to the questions asked relating to solving the Diophantine equation related to the GCF, Euclidean Division Algorithm, linear combination, special solution theorem, and general solution of an equation. These results indicate that the subject of FICS thinks logically in formulating a plan to complete the model by relating the situation to the concept as stated by Keraf (1999).

These results indicate that the subject of FICS in planning a solution can reason, as Keraf (1999) argues that the notion of reasoning is a thought process that tries to connect known facts or evidence to a conclusion. These results indicate that the FICS in planning the solution can reasoning adaptive, as stated by NRC (2001) that the notion of adaptive reasoning refers to the capacity to think logically about the relationship between concepts and situations.

Table 1. Interview Results of FDCS Subjects and FICS Subjects at the Stage of Planning Solutions in Solving Mathematical Problems

Making plan a model by linking the situation with the concept
FDCS relates the number of stalls, the number of boxes with the concept of coefficients, the number of bonus oranges with constants, and the number of oranges in each stall and box with variables in the Diophantine equation, while FICS relates the number of oranges in each box and the number of oranges in each stall with the variables. , linking the number of Pak Ahmad's stalls with the coefficient of the variable x , and the number of boxes with the coefficient of the variable y , linking the number of bonuses of oranges with constants and linking the conditions given to the concept of conditions of solutions or constraints that used to determine the Diophantine equation
Explain the reason for planning in making a model by relating the situation to the concept
FDCS explains plain to make it easier to work when the situation in the problem is for example the concepts of variables, coefficients, and constants it will make it easier to work on, while FICS explains that the situation described in the problem if translated into a mathematical model following the definition of the Diophantine equation with the form of the equation $ax + by = c$, where a, b, c are integers, and $a, b \neq 0$.
Develop a plan in making a model by relating the situation to the situation
FDCS determines the number of oranges received by each stall is related to the number of stalls owned by Mr. Ahmad, namely 57, and the number of oranges in each box is related to the boxes purchased by Mr. Ahmad is 158 boxes, while FICS determines the relationship between the number of stalls, the number of boxes, the number of bonus oranges given related to the number of oranges for each box is the same, and the number of oranges for each stall that is distributed equally fulfills the given conditions.
Explain the reasons for making plans in making models by relating situations to situation
FDCS explained that the known and asked situations were related. While FICS explained that according to the information in the interrelated questions, the number of oranges in each box was the same, and the number of oranges distributed in each stall met the requirements given.
Explain the reasons for making plans in making models by linking concepts with concepts
FDCS relates the concepts of variables, coefficients, and constants to the concept of the Diophantine equation, while FICS links the concept of the Diophantine equation to the concept of coefficients, the concept of variables, and the concept of constants, as well as the concept of requirements for problem solutions.
Explain the reasons for making plans in making models by linking concepts with concepts
FDCS explains that when the equation is converted into a mathematical model using the concepts of variables, coefficients, and constants, it will be the same as the general form of the Diophantine equation, while FICS explains that based on the information contained in the problem, it is following the definitions and requirements of the Diophantine equation.
Develop a plan in completing the model by linking concepts with concepts
FDCS completes the model using the Euclides Algorithm to find the GCF from the number that states the number of stalls and the number of boxes, then proves or declares the GCF as a linear combination of the two numbers, then solves the obtained equation by changing the equation according to the information in

the problem, while FICS solves the Diophantine equation by linking it with the GCF concept using the Euclidean Division Algorithm, linear combination, specific solution of an equation, a general solution of an equation, a conditional problem solution.

Explain the reasons for making plans in completing the model by linking concepts with concepts

FDCS explained that with the linkage of the planned concept the results would be obtained faster, while the FICS explained value of the variable was the answer to the questions asked related to the concept of solving the Diophantine equation related to the GCF concept, Euclidean Division Algorithm, Linear combination, application the theorem and the general solution of an equation and initial conditions for the problem.

Table 1 show that FICS subjects are analytical in connecting concepts with problem situations, while FDCS subjects have difficulty finding relationships situations and concepts. Following the opinion of Almolhodaei (2002). The difference is caused by the characteristics of the subject in solving mathematical problems as expressed (Bahrami & Yousefi, 2011; Coop & Sigel, 1971; Minarni, 2010; Nurmutia, 2019; Witkin et al., 1977; Aning W. Yanti et al., 2020; Aning Wida Yanti et al., 2020).

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results of data analysis and discussion, the profile of students' adaptive reasoning with FDCS and FICS at the stage of planning solutions in Solving Mathematical Problems is as follows: Students with FDCS: make plans that are less detailed and incomplete, think globally and find it difficult to focus attention, cannot relate situations and situations or concepts to concepts, provide logical reasons for some of the steps taken. Meanwhile, students with FICS: make plans that are quite detailed and complete using appropriate concepts, think analytically and systematically in relating situations to situations and concept to concept, process information with their structure, provide logical reasons for each step taken.

SUGGESTIONS

Based on the conclusions of the research results, for further research, it can be seen the profile of students' adaptive reasoning based on other aspects such as male gender, high and low mathematical abilities, learning styles, or another cognitive aspect.

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